

Image Contraction under Random Composition of a Fixed Function Family

Mattia Castriotta

June 2, 2026

Abstract

Fix a finite family of maps, \mathcal{F} , on $[N]$, and compose them in an i.i.d. uniform random order. The successive image sets then define a Markov chain on a finite reachability graph and its strongly connected component (SCC) decomposition gives the asymptotic contraction. Assuming the profile falls all the way to its floor, $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = 1$, we obtain an exact formula for the contraction profile $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) = \mathbb{E}[|X_m|]$ (Theorem 4.2), a geometric decay at rate λ_* (Theorem 5.2) and the spectral identity $\rho(Q_{\text{pairs}}) = \lambda_*$ for the induced pair chain (Proposition 8.1). Furthermore, we derive a lower bound on the synchronisation time for a natural class of examples, an $O(N \log N)$ bound for refreshed maps (the fixed-family case is Q2) and the exact two-point function of the contraction process (Proposition 8.6). We close with five open problems.

1 Introduction

We have $\mathcal{F} = \{f_1, \dots, f_I\}$ on $[N] := \{0, \dots, N-1\}$, and we draw $\sigma(0), \sigma(1), \dots$ independently and uniformly from $\{1, \dots, I\}$, then set $F_m := f_{\sigma(m-1)} \circ \dots \circ f_{\sigma(0)}$ for $m \geq 1$, with $F_m(S) := \{F_m(s) : s \in S\}$. The law of $\text{Im}(F_1)$ under one random map is $p_0(S) := |\{i : f_i([N]) = S\}|/I$. Set $X_0 := \text{Im}(F_1)$, which has law p_0 , and $X_{m+1} := f_{\sigma(m+1)}(X_m)$. Then $X_m = \text{Im}(F_{m+1})$ for $m \geq 0$, so X_0 is the first image. Because $|f(S)| \leq |S|$, the sequence $|X_m|$ never grows. Define $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) := \mathbb{E}[|X_m|]$ for the *contraction profile*.

The chain lives on the reachability graph $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{F})$: its vertices are the image sets $\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F}) = \{\text{Im}(f_{i_k} \circ \dots \circ f_{i_1}) : k \geq 1\}$, and an edge $S \rightarrow f_i(S)$ carries weight $1/I$. From the graph and its SCC decomposition we read off the four quantities computed below: the limit $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty)$, the rate at which $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty)$ decays, the law of the synchronisation time and the two-point function of $(|X_m|)$. All four come down to the transient block Q and its spectral radius (Proposition 8.1).

When we draw a fresh map at each step, Dalal-Schmutz [2] read the expected synchronisation time off exchangeability alone. For a fixed family exchangeability fails, and one analyses the image-set chain directly. The fixed-automaton, random-input model we work in is the one studied by Gusev [8], where $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}]$ can be exponential once the family is adversarial. For a random family, Berlinkov [9] shows a binary family synchronises with probability $1 - \Theta(1/N)$, so conditioning on synchronisation changes almost nothing; Chapuy and Péarnau [10] and Martinsson [11] bound the *shortest* reset word by $O(\sqrt{N} \log N)$, a different quantity from the random-input $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}]$. Černý [5] and Szykuła [6] bound worst-case reset words. Here, the word is random and the observable is image size. We are not aware of the reachability-graph viewpoint or the exact formula (3) appearing elsewhere.

2 The reachability graph

Throughout, distributions are column vectors and p^\top is the matching row vector.

Definition 2.1. $\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F}) := \{\text{Im}(f_{i_k} \circ \dots \circ f_{i_1}) : k \geq 1, i_j \in [I]\}$, $[I] := \{1, \dots, I\}$. The graph $\mathcal{G}(\mathcal{F})$ has vertex set $\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})$ and a directed edge $S \rightarrow f_i(S)$ of weight $1/I$ per S, i , with $f_i(S) := \{f_i(s) : s \in S\}$. An SCC is *absorbing* if it has no outgoing edges.

Lemma 2.2. $f_i(S) \in \text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})$ for all $S \in \text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})$, $i \in [I]$; and $|\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})| \leq 2^N$.

Proof. $f_i(\text{Im}(f_{i_k} \circ \dots \circ f_{i_1})) = \text{Im}(f_i \circ f_{i_k} \circ \dots \circ f_{i_1}) \in \text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})$. \square

So $P(S, S') := |\{i : f_i(S) = S'\}|/I$ is stochastic on $\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})$.

Definition 2.3. $p_0(S) := |\{i : f_i([N]) = S\}|/I$, $X_0 := \text{Im}(F_1) \sim p_0$, $X_{m+1} := f_{\sigma(m+1)}(X_m)$ so that $X_m = \text{Im}(F_{m+1})$ and $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) := \mathbb{E}[|X_m|]$.

Proposition 2.4. $(X_m)_{m \geq 0}$ is a homogeneous Markov chain on $\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})$ with matrix P , and $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) = p_0^\top P^m g$ for all $m \geq 0$, where $g(S) := |S|$, $P^0 := I$.

Proof. Since $\sigma(m+1)$ is independent of X_0, \dots, X_m , the recursion $X_{m+1} = f_{\sigma(m+1)}(X_m)$ is a Markov chain with transition matrix P ; hence $\mathbb{P}(X_m = S) = (p_0^\top P^m)_S$ and $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) = \mathbb{E}[g(X_m)] = p_0^\top P^m g$. \square

3 The limit theorem

Label the absorbing SCCs C_1, \dots, C_ℓ , let Q be the transient-to-transient block of P and put $R_j(S) := \sum_{S' \in C_j} P(S, S')$ on the transient states.

Lemma 3.1. $\rho(Q) < 1$.

Proof. Each transient state reaches an absorbing SCC within $n := |\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})|$ steps along edges of weight $\geq 1/I$, so $\|Q^n\|_{\infty \rightarrow \infty} \leq 1 - (1/I)^n$ and therefore $\rho(Q) \leq (1 - (1/I)^n)^{1/n} < 1$. \square

Lemma 3.2. (X_m) is absorbed a.s. With $B(\cdot, j) := (I - Q)^{-1} R_j$,

$$\pi_j := \mathbb{P}_{p_0}(\text{absorbed in } C_j) = p_0^\top |_{\text{tr}} B(\cdot, j) + p_0^\top |_{C_j} \mathbf{1}_{C_j}, \quad \sum_j \pi_j = 1 \quad (1)$$

Proof. Absorption holds a.s. since $\rho(Q) < 1$. Conditioning on the first step gives $(I - Q)B(\cdot, j) = R_j$, hence (1); and the absorption probabilities sum to 1 because the chain is absorbed almost surely, so some C_j is reached with probability one. \square

Each C_j carries a unique stationary law μ_j and the time-averages of any bounded functional under $P|_{C_j}$ settle to its μ_j -mean [7, Thms 1.7, 4.9].

Lemma 3.3. For bounded ϕ and any starting law ν_0 on C_j , the time-averages $\frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m \mathbb{E}_{\nu_0}[\phi(X_t)]$ tend to $\mu_j(\phi)$; and if $P|_{C_j}$ is aperiodic then already $\mathbb{E}_{\nu_0}[\phi(X_t)] \rightarrow \mu_j(\phi)$, without averaging.

Remark. A loop $P(S, S) > 0$ (some f_i fixes S setwise) already forces aperiodicity. In the sampling of Section 6 every absorbing SCC was aperiodic, so the Cesàro average above was never actually needed.

Theorem 3.4. $\frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(t) \rightarrow \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) := \sum_{j=1}^{\ell} \pi_j \mu_j(g)$, with $\mu_j(g) := \sum_{S \in C_j} \mu_j(S) |S|$. If every $P|_{C_j}$ is aperiodic, then $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) \rightarrow \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty)$.

Proof. $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(t) = A(t) + \sum_j B_j(t)$, where $A(t) := \mathbb{E}[|X_t|; X_t \text{ transient}]$ and $B_j(t) := \mathbb{E}[|X_t|; X_t \in C_j]$. Lemma 3.1 forces $A(t) \leq N \mathbb{P}(X_t \text{ transient}) \rightarrow 0$.

Let $\tau_j := \inf\{t \geq 0 : X_t \in C_j\}$ and $\nu_r := \text{Law}(X_r \mid \tau_j = r)$. As C_j is absorbing, $\{X_t \in C_j\} = \{\tau_j \leq t\}$ and the strong Markov property gives

$$B_j(t) = \sum_{r=0}^t \mathbb{P}(\tau_j = r) \mathbb{E}_{\nu_r}[g(X_{t-r})] \quad (2)$$

Paths absorbed elsewhere have $\tau_j = \infty$, so $\sum_{r \geq 0} \mathbb{P}(\tau_j = r) = \pi_j \leq 1$. Interchanging the finite sums,

$$\frac{1}{m} \sum_{t=1}^m B_j(t) = \sum_{r=0}^m \mathbb{P}(\tau_j = r) \cdot \frac{1}{m} \sum_{s=0}^{m-r} \mathbb{E}_{\nu_r}[g(X_s)]$$

Fix $\varepsilon > 0$ and choose R with $\sum_{r > R} \mathbb{P}(\tau_j = r) < \varepsilon/(2N)$; the $r > R$ tail is then below $\varepsilon/2$. For each $r \leq R$, Lemma 3.3 drives the inner average to $\mu_j(g)$, so for large m the head lies within $\varepsilon/2$ of $\sum_{r \leq R} \mathbb{P}(\tau_j = r) \mu_j(g)$. Letting $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ leaves $\frac{1}{m} \sum_t B_j(t) \rightarrow \pi_j \mu_j(g)$ and summing over j gives the Cesàro statement. If every $P|_{C_j}$ is aperiodic the inner limits hold pointwise, and the same estimate gives $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) \rightarrow \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty)$ directly. \square

4 Synchronisation and the Exact Formula

Proposition 4.1. $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = 1$ if and only if every state in every absorbing SCC is a singleton. A constant map in the monoid $\langle \mathcal{F} \rangle$ already forces this.

Proof. If all absorbing SCCs are singletons then $\mu_j(g) = 1$ and $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = \sum_j \pi_j = 1$. If some absorbing C_j contains a non-singleton S , then $\mu_j(S) > 0$ (finite irreducible chain), so $\mu_j(g) = 1 + \sum_{S' \in C_j} \mu_j(S')(|S'| - 1) \geq 1 + \mu_j(S)(|S| - 1) > 1$ and $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) > 1$.

For the last sentence, suppose $\langle \mathcal{F} \rangle$ has a constant map, so some $\{c\}$ is reachable from every vertex. If an absorbing C_j contained a non-singleton, the path from it to $\{c\}$ would stay inside C_j , forcing $\{c\} \in C_j$; strong connectivity would then make every node of C_j reachable from $\{c\}$, yet iterating any f_i out of a singleton only gives singletons. So no such C_j exists. \square

Remark. We say the family synchronises when the monoid $\langle \mathcal{F} \rangle$ contains a constant map, a strictly stronger demand than $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = 1$.

Throughout §4-8 we assume $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = 1$, so every non-singleton state is transient.

Theorem 4.2. If $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = 1$, then for all $m \geq 0$,

$$\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) = 1 + p_0^\top Q^m h_0, \quad h_0 := g_{\text{ns}} - \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}, \quad (3)$$

where $g_{\text{ns}}(S) := |S|$ and $\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$ is the all-ones vector on non-singletons.

Proof. Write $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1 = p_0^\top P^m (g - \mathbf{1})$. Singletons are absorbing, so P^m moves no mass from them back to the non-singletons: $(P^m)_{\text{si}, \text{ns}} = 0$ and $(P^m)_{\text{ns}, \text{ns}} = Q^m$. Since $g - \mathbf{1}$ vanishes on singletons, only the non-singleton block survives, and that is (3). \square

Remark. If Q is diagonalisable, then $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) = 1 + \sum_\lambda c_\lambda \lambda^m$, with $c_\lambda = (p_0^\top \varphi_\lambda)(\psi_\lambda^\top h_0)$ for eigenpairs normalised by $\psi_\lambda^\top \varphi_\lambda = 1$. Section 6 checks this against the direct evaluation $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) = p_0^\top P^m g$.

Corollary 4.3. $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m+1) \leq \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m)$.

Proof. $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m+1) = \mathbb{E}[|f_{\sigma(m)}(X_m)|] \leq \mathbb{E}[|X_m|] = \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m)$. \square

5 Geometric Decay

Proposition 5.1. *On the non-singleton states Q is block lower-triangular with diagonal blocks $Q_{k,k}$, $k = N, \dots, 2$, since a step never enlarges a set and a singleton stays one; write Q_{ns} for this non-singleton block and set $\lambda_* := \rho(Q_{\text{ns}}) = \max_{k \geq 2} \rho(Q_{k,k})$ [1, Thm 1.3.3]. As h_0 lives on the non-singletons, $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1 = (p_0|_{\text{ns}})^\top Q_{\text{ns}}^m h_0$, so λ_* is the genuine decay rate.*

Remark. *If $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = 1$, each absorbing SCC is a singleton and $P|_{C_j} = [1]$, so every eigenvalue of P with $|\mu| < 1$ lies in Q ; of these, the ones carried by the non-singleton block Q_{ns} have largest modulus λ_* . Drop the assumption and the absorbing blocks may carry sub-unit eigenvalues, which breaks this.*

Remark. *In most cases the maximum in Proposition 5.1 sits at $k = 2$ ($N \leq 12$, $I \leq 5$), but not always. For $N = 6$, $I = 2$ with $f_1 = (0, 5, 1, 4, 0, 0)$ and $f_2 = (0, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0)$ one finds $\rho(Q_{2,2}) = 0$ while $\rho(Q_{3,3}) = \rho(Q_{5,5}) = 1/2 = \lambda_*$, so the maximum is reached at $k = 3$ and $k = 5$ and never at $k = 2$. See Q1.*

Theorem 5.2. $|\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1| = O(m^{r-1} \lambda_*^m)$, where r is the size of the largest Jordan block of Q_{ns} at λ_* .

Proof. $|\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1| = |(p_0|_{\text{ns}})^\top Q_{\text{ns}}^m h_0|$ by (3),

with $Q_{\text{ns}} = VJV^{-1}$, $|\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1| \leq \|p_0|_{\text{ns}}\|_1 \|V\| \|J^m\| \|V^{-1}\| \|h_0\|_\infty$ and $\|J^m\| = O(m^{r-1} \lambda_*^m)$ [1, §5.6]. \square

6 Numerical Experiments

All computations below can be reproduced with the notebook at <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1dBjw6Jm3YnSI6JajZ5mJ6nloZFpskXf0>

We sample each map by drawing its N values independently and uniformly from $[N]$. Table 1 sets the predicted $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty)$ of Theorem 3.4 against a Monte Carlo estimate, the chain run for 120 steps and $|X_{120}|$ averaged over 3000 runs. On a synchronising family both equal 1; on the others the difference is Monte Carlo noise of order $\sigma/\sqrt{3000} = O(10^{-2})$. The last column counts the families on which the two agree to 10^{-3} , which tracks the synchronisation rate, the residual on non-synchronising families being sampling noise of that order.

Table 1: $|\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}^{\text{pred}}(\infty) - \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}^{\text{MC}}(\infty)|$ over random families (seed 2026). The error is dominated by Monte Carlo sampling on the non-synchronising families.

N	I	families	mean	max	frac $< 10^{-3}$
6	2	80	8.6×10^{-3}	3.0×10^{-1}	70/80
6	3	80	2.0×10^{-3}	9.2×10^{-2}	73/80
8	2	50	2.2×10^{-2}	7.2×10^{-1}	36/50
8	3	50	2.0×10^{-4}	4.7×10^{-3}	47/50
10	2	30	1.0×10^{-2}	2.1×10^{-1}	21/30
10	3	30	3.4×10^{-4}	4.3×10^{-3}	27/30

For 60 synchronising families with $N = 8$, the Pearson correlation between λ_* and the empirical decay rate of $|\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1|$ is 0.99, as Theorem 5.2 predicts.

7 Worked Example

Take $N = 4$ and $I = 2$ with $f_1 = (0, 0, 1, 1)$ and $f_2 = (0, 1, 0, 1)$. Both maps fold [4] onto $\{0, 1\}$, so the first image is always $\{0, 1\}$ and $p_0(\{0, 1\}) = 1$. Writing $s := \{0, 1\}$, one further step

sends s either to $\{0\}$ (under f_1) or back to itself (under f_2), so the whole reachability graph is $\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F}) = \{\{0\}, s\}$ and

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad Q = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \lambda_* = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = 1$$

Then $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(0) = 2$ and $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) = 1 + 2^{-m}$ thereafter. The hitting time is $h(s) = 2$, and with $\alpha = 1$ this is $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = p_0^\top h = 2$. The Perron vector is $v = [1]$, giving $c = 1 \geq 1/I$; here $Q\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \lambda_* v$ exactly, so the bound of Theorem 8.2 is attained.

8 Synchronisation Time

$T_{\text{sync}} := \min\{m \geq 1 : |X_m| = 1\}$, $\alpha := \mathbb{P}(|X_0| \geq 2)$. The hitting vector $h := (I - Q)^{-1}\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$ satisfies $h(S) = \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}} \mid X_0 = S]$ on non-singletons. The tail sum $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = \sum_{m \geq 0} \mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} > m)$ has $\mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} > 0) = 1$ and, for $m \geq 1$, $\mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} > m) = \mathbb{P}(|X_m| \geq 2) = p_0^\top |_{\text{ns}} Q^m \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$ (at $m = 0$ the right side is α , not 1). Summing the $m \geq 1$ tail with $\sum_{m \geq 1} Q^m = Q(I - Q)^{-1}$,

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = 1 + p_0^\top |_{\text{ns}} Q(I - Q)^{-1} \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = 1 + p_0^\top |_{\text{ns}} (h - \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}) = 1 - \alpha + p_0^\top h, \quad (4)$$

which equals $p_0^\top h$ when $\alpha = 1$.

The vector v . We want a nonnegative λ_* -eigenvector of Q_{ns} that is also monotone under inclusion; the monotonicity is what later forces $c \geq 1/I$ in Theorem 8.5. The natural source is the resolvent: at $s = \lambda_*$ the spectral radius is a pole of $(sI - Q_{\text{ns}})^{-1}$ and the normalised residue there is a nonnegative eigenvector. Reading v off the resolvent rather than taking an abstract Perron vector keeps the monotonicity visible, since the resolvent is assembled from the monotone iterates w_k . Set $w_k := Q_{\text{ns}}^k \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$, so $w_k(S) = \mathbb{P}_S(|F_k| \geq 2)$ is the chance that k random maps have not yet collapsed S to a point. Each w_k is monotone under inclusion, since $A \supseteq B$ forces $|F_k(A)| \geq |F_k(B)|$ pathwise, and $0 \leq w_k \leq \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$. For $s > \lambda_*$ the resolvent $(sI - Q_{\text{ns}})^{-1} = \sum_{k \geq 0} s^{-k-1} Q_{\text{ns}}^k$ is nonnegative, so

$$\phi_s := (sI - Q_{\text{ns}})^{-1} \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \sum_{k \geq 0} s^{-k-1} w_k$$

is nonnegative and monotone, with $Q_{\text{ns}} \phi_s = s \phi_s - \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$. If $u \geq 0$ is a left eigenvector $u^\top Q_{\text{ns}} = \lambda_* u^\top$ then $u^\top \phi_s = (s - \lambda_*)^{-1} u^\top \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} \rightarrow \infty$, so $\|\phi_s\|_\infty \rightarrow \infty$ as $s \downarrow \lambda_*$. Along a sequence $s_n \downarrow \lambda_*$ for which $\phi_{s_n} / \|\phi_{s_n}\|_\infty$ converges (one exists by compactness) put $v := \lim_n \phi_{s_n} / \|\phi_{s_n}\|_\infty$. Then $v \geq 0$, $\|v\|_\infty = 1$, v is monotone and $v \leq \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$; dividing $Q_{\text{ns}} \phi_s = s \phi_s - \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$ by $\|\phi_s\|_\infty$ and letting $s_n \downarrow \lambda_*$ gives $Q_{\text{ns}} v = \lambda_* v$. Fix S_* with $v(S_*) = 1$ and set $p_0^{\text{cond}} := p_0 |_{\text{ns}} / \alpha$, $c := (p_0^{\text{cond}})^\top v$.

8.1 The pair chain

Proposition 8.1. *For a synchronising family \mathcal{F} with $\lambda_* > 0$, $\rho(Q_{\text{pairs}}) = \lambda_*$, where Q_{pairs} acts on $\Omega_2 := \{\{a, b\} : a \neq b\}$ by $Q_{\text{pairs}}(\{a, b\}, \{c, d\}) = |\{i : f_i(\{a, b\}) = \{c, d\}, c \neq d\}| / I$, absorbing to \dagger when $f_i(a) = f_i(b)$.*

Proof. For nonnegative Q_{pairs} , $\|Q_{\text{pairs}}^k\|_{\infty \rightarrow \infty} = \|Q_{\text{pairs}}^k \mathbf{1}\|_\infty$ and $(Q_{\text{pairs}}^k \mathbf{1})_{\{a, b\}} = \mathbb{P}(F_k(a) \neq F_k(b))$.

Since $F_k(a) \neq F_k(b)$ forces $|F_k([N])| \geq 2$, for every pair

$$(Q_{\text{pairs}}^k \mathbf{1})_{\{a, b\}} \leq \mathbb{P}(|F_k([N])| \geq 2) \leq \mathbb{E}[|F_k([N])| - 1] = \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(k - 1) - 1 = O(k^{r-1} \lambda_*^k)$$

by Theorem 5.2. Hence $\|Q_{\text{pairs}}^k\|_{\infty \rightarrow \infty} = O(k^{r-1} \lambda_*^k)$ and Gelfand gives $\rho(Q_{\text{pairs}}) \leq \lambda_*$.

For the matching lower bound, since $\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} > 0$ and $Q_{\text{ns}} \geq 0$ has radius λ_* , $\|Q_{\text{ns}}^k \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}\|_\infty^{1/k} \rightarrow \lambda_*$; pick S_k attaining the maximum, $(Q_{\text{ns}}^k \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}})_{S_k} = \|Q_{\text{ns}}^k \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}\|_\infty$. As $\{|F_k(S_k)| \geq 2\} = \bigcup_{\{a,b\} \subseteq S_k} \{F_k(a) \neq F_k(b)\}$, the union bound gives

$$\|Q_{\text{pairs}}^k \mathbf{1}\|_\infty \geq \max_{\{a,b\} \subseteq S_k} \mathbb{P}(F_k(a) \neq F_k(b)) \geq \frac{(Q_{\text{ns}}^k \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}})_{S_k}}{\binom{N}{2}} = \frac{\|Q_{\text{ns}}^k \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}\|_\infty}{\binom{N}{2}}$$

Hence $\|Q_{\text{pairs}}^k \mathbf{1}\|_\infty^{1/k} \rightarrow \lambda_*$ and Gelfand gives $\rho(Q_{\text{pairs}}) \geq \lambda_*$. \square

8.2 A lower bound

Theorem 8.2. *If $\alpha > 0$, $\lambda_* > 0$, then $c > 0$ and*

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] \geq \alpha \left(1 + \frac{c\lambda_*}{1-\lambda_*}\right), \quad (5)$$

with equality when $\alpha = 1$ and $Q\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \lambda_*v$.

Proof. With $1 \geq \alpha$,

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = 1 + \sum_{m \geq 1} p_0^\top |_{\text{ns}} Q^m \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} \geq \alpha + \alpha \sum_{m \geq 1} \mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} > m \mid |X_0| \geq 2),$$

using $p_0^\top |_{\text{ns}} Q^m \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \alpha(p_0^{\text{cond}})^\top Q^m \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$. From $v \leq \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}}$ and $Q^m v = \lambda_*^m v$, $(Q^m \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}})_S \geq \lambda_*^m v(S)$, and averaging under p_0^{cond} gives $\mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} > m \mid |X_0| \geq 2) \geq c\lambda_*^m$; summing the geometric series over $m \geq 1$ yields (5).

It remains to check $c > 0$. At S_* the relation $Qv = \lambda_*v$ reads $\lambda_* = \frac{1}{I} \sum_i v(f_i(S_*)) \mathbf{1}_{f_i(S_*) \in \text{ns}}$, which is positive, so $v(S') > 0$ for some $S' = f_j(S_*) \in \text{ns}$. A path reaching S' never meets a singleton, since those absorb, and its start $S_0 = f_{i_0}([N])$ lies in ns with $Q^r(S_0, S') > 0$ for some r ; then $\lambda_*^r v(S_0) \geq Q^r(S_0, S')v(S') > 0$, so $v(S_0) > 0$, and $p_0(S_0) \geq 1/I$ forces $c > 0$.

Equality is the case $Q\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \lambda_*v$, where $Q^m \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \lambda_*^m v$ and each inequality above becomes an equality. \square

Remark. *In the worked example $\alpha = 1$ and $Q\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \lambda_*v$, so $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = 2$ and the bound is tight.*

Example 8.3. $N = 4$, $I = 3$, $f_1 = (0, 0, 0, 1)$, $f_2 = (1, 1, 1, 0)$, $f_3 = (2, 2, 1, 2)$. On $\{0, 1\}, \{1, 2\}$, $Q = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/3 \end{pmatrix}$, $\lambda_* = 1/3$, $v = (0, 1)^\top$, $c = 1/3 = 1/I$, $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = 7/6$; equality since $Q\mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} = \lambda_*v$.

Remark. *A search over 3×10^4 synchronising families ($N \leq 6$, $I \leq 4$) gave smallest ratio $\mathbb{E}[T](1-\lambda_*)/\alpha = 3/4$, at $N = 4$, $I = 2$, $\lambda_* = 1/2$. The family $Q = \text{diag}(1-\delta, 0)$, $p_0 = (1/2, 1/2)$, $\alpha = 1$ has ratio $(1+\delta)/2$, which approaches $1/2$ without attaining it.*

Table 2: $Q = \text{diag}(1-\delta, 0)$, $p_0 = (1/2, 1/2)$, $\alpha = 1$.

δ	λ_*	$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}]$	ratio
1/2	1/2	3/2	3/4
1/4	3/4	5/2	5/8
1/n	$1 - 1/n$	$(n+1)/2$	$(n+1)/(2n) \rightarrow 1/2$

8.3 The overlap c

Lemma 8.4. $A \supseteq B$, $|B| \geq 2 \Rightarrow v(A) \geq v(B)$.

Proof. Each w_k is monotone, hence so is $\phi_s = \sum_k s^{-k-1} w_k$, and the property survives the normalised limit defining v . \square

Theorem 8.5. $c \geq 1/I$, so $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] \geq \alpha(1 + \lambda_*/(I(1 - \lambda_*)))$.

Proof. Some SCC T of Q_{ns} has $\rho(Q|_T) = \lambda_*$; being strongly connected, each $S \in T$ has $f_j(S) \in T$ for some j , so the row sums of $Q|_T$ are $\geq 1/I$ and $\lambda_* = \rho(Q|_T) \geq 1/I$. At S_* , $(Q_{\text{ns}}v)_{S_*} = \lambda_*$ reads $\sum_i v(f_i(S_*)) \mathbf{1}_{f_i(S_*) \in \text{ns}} = I\lambda_*$. Since $f_i(S_*) \subseteq f_i([N])$, Lemma 8.4 gives $v(f_i([N])) \geq v(f_i(S_*))$ (and $f_i(S_*) \in \text{ns}$ forces $f_i([N]) \in \text{ns}$), so $\sum_i v(f_i([N])) \mathbf{1}_{\text{ns}} \geq I\lambda_*$. The left side is $I\alpha c$, so $I\alpha c \geq I\lambda_* \geq 1$ and $c \geq 1/I$. \square

8.4 The two-point function

If all non-singleton states have the same size, the two-point function becomes explicit; the same computation also rules out a functional CLT (Q5).

Proposition 8.6. Assume $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty) = 1$ and that every non-singleton state in $\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})$ has the same cardinality $\gamma \geq 2$ (distinct from the overlap c of Theorem 8.2). Put $p_m := \mathbb{P}(|X_m| \geq 2) = (\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1)/(\gamma - 1)$. For all $m, k \geq 0$,

$$\text{Cov}(|X_m|, |X_{m+k}|) = (\gamma - 1)^2 p_{m+k}(1 - p_m), \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Corr}(|X_m|, |X_{m+k}|) = \sqrt{\frac{p_{m+k}(1 - p_m)}{p_m(1 - p_{m+k})}} \quad (7)$$

If moreover the Perron mode of Q at λ_* is excited ($c > 0$ in Theorem 8.2, equivalently $\lim_m (\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m) - 1)^{1/m} = \lambda_*$), then for fixed k , $\text{Corr}(|X_m|, |X_{m+k}|) \rightarrow \lambda_*^{k/2}$ as $m \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. $|X_m| \in \{1, \gamma\}$, so $|X_m| = 1 + (\gamma - 1)B_m$, $B_m := \mathbf{1}[|X_m| = \gamma]$. Since singletons absorb, $\{|X_{m+k}| \geq 2\} \subseteq \{|X_m| \geq 2\}$, so $\mathbb{P}(B_m = 1, B_{m+k} = 1) = p_{m+k}$ and $\mathbb{P}(B_m = 0, B_{m+k} = 1) = 0$. Then

$$\mathbb{E}[|X_m||X_{m+k}|] = \gamma^2 p_{m+k} + \gamma(p_m - p_{m+k}) + (1 - p_m) = 1 + (\gamma - 1)p_m + \gamma(\gamma - 1)p_{m+k},$$

and subtracting $\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m)\kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m+k) = (1 + (\gamma - 1)p_m)(1 + (\gamma - 1)p_{m+k})$ leaves (6). With $\text{Var}(|X_m|) = (\gamma - 1)^2 p_m(1 - p_m)$, dividing gives (7). For the last claim, an excited Perron mode means $p_m \sim a \lambda_*^m$ with $a > 0$, so $p_{m+k}/p_m \rightarrow \lambda_*^k$; sending $p_m, p_{m+k} \rightarrow 0$ in (7) leaves $\lambda_*^{k/2}$. \square

Remark. $\text{Var}(|X_m|) = (\gamma - 1)^2 p_m(1 - p_m) \rightarrow 0$, so the centred process $Z_m := |X_m| - \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m)$ has summable variance and, by (6), summable covariances; $\text{Var}(\sum_{m=0}^M Z_m)$ settles to a finite limit as $M \rightarrow \infty$ (e.g. 2 in the worked example). The partial sums show no \sqrt{M} growth and admit no Donsker scaling: the walk is absorbed and never settles into a stationary regime. A functional CLT in the sense of Q5 must therefore concern a different object, the pre-absorption excursion $(|X_{\lfloor tT_{\text{sync}} \rfloor}|)_{t \in [0,1]}$, say, or a time-change that compensates for the decay. We have not worked on either.

8.5 The refresh model

For a fixed family \mathcal{F} the reused map is correlated with the current image, which is the difficulty in Q2. With a fresh map at each step that correlation is absent, and the bound below reduces to a coupon-collector estimate.

Proposition 8.7 (Refresh model). *Let g_1, g_2, \dots be i.i.d. uniform on $[N]^{[N]}$, $Y_0 := [N]$, $Y_{m+1} := g_{m+1}(Y_m)$, and $T := \min\{m : |Y_m| = 1\}$. Then $\mathbb{E}[T] \leq NH_{N-1} \leq N(\ln N + 1)$.*

Proof. $(|Y_m|)$ is a Markov chain on $\{1, \dots, N\}$ and $g_{m+1} \perp Y_m$, so for $|Y_m| = k \geq 2$,

$$\mathbb{P}(g_{m+1}|_{Y_m} \text{ injective}) = \prod_{j=0}^{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{j}{N}\right) = \left(1 - \frac{k-1}{N}\right) \prod_{j=1}^{k-2} \left(1 - \frac{j}{N}\right) \leq 1 - \frac{k-1}{N},$$

the trailing factors being ≤ 1 . So from size k the chain strictly drops with probability $\geq (k-1)/N$ at every step; the time it spends at size k is dominated by a geometric variable of mean $\leq N/(k-1)$, and summing over $k = 2, \dots, N$ gives $\mathbb{E}[T] \leq \sum_{k=2}^N N/(k-1) = NH_{N-1}$. \square

With fresh maps this is a well-known result (see, e.g., [2]). The gap between the two is what reuse costs.

Remark. *For a fixed \mathcal{F} the step map $f_{\sigma(m+1)}$ has the same uniform marginal but is reused, hence correlated with $X_m = \text{Im}(F_{m+1})$, built from those same maps. A reused map already revealed on X_m may be injective there, so the per-step bound $(k-1)/N$ can fail outright at a given step and the argument above does not transfer verbatim. The same NH_{N-1} bound is still the natural guess and it holds across random families in simulation (borderline at $N = 5$, within sampling error); proving it needs a reuse-aware coupling, the upper-bound half of Q2.*

Remark. *The bound is only an average and a single synchronising \mathcal{F} can sit well above it. For $N = 4$, $I = 3$ with $f_1 = (3, 0, 3, 1)$, $f_2 = (3, 2, 1, 1)$, $f_3 = (1, 1, 1, 3)$, the set $\{0, 1, 3\}$ takes $h(\{0, 1, 3\}) \approx 9.15$ to absorb, past $NH_3 = 7.33$.*

Conjecture 8.8. *Let the maps f_1, \dots, f_I ($I \geq 2$) be i.i.d. uniform on $[N]^{[N]}$. For every non-singleton S there is a constant $c_0 > 0$, independent of N and S , with $\mathbb{P}(|F_N(S)| = 1) \geq c_0$ for all $N \geq 2$. At $S = [N]$, where the image has the furthest to fall, simulation gives $\mathbb{P}(|F_N([N])| = 1)$ between 0.19 and 0.38 for $I = 2$ ($N = 4, \dots, 32$): it decreases slowly and stays bounded away from 0 over this range, consistent with $c_0 > 0$ though not establishing it.*

Remark. *We do not have a proof. Heuristically, by [4] a random map settles onto a cycle of length $\Theta(\sqrt{N})$ after $\Theta(\sqrt{N})$ iterates; with $I = 2$ and $N/4 \gg \sqrt{N}$ steps to spare, a positive fraction of trajectories reach a singleton. A proof would need quantitative control of the cycle lengths and their intersections, which is beyond us here.*

Theorem 8.9. *Under Conjecture 8.8, $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] \leq N/c_0 = O(N)$.*

Proof. $\mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} > kN) \leq (1 - c_0)^k$ by induction, so $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] \leq N \sum_{k \geq 0} (1 - c_0)^k = N/c_0$. \square

Lemma 8.10 (Perron regularity and hitting times). *Let $Q \geq 0$ be irreducible and substochastic with $\rho(Q) = \lambda_* < 1$ and right Perron vector $\varphi > 0$ and put $\Phi := \varphi_{\max}/\varphi_{\min}$. The hitting vector $h := (I - Q)^{-1}\mathbf{1} = \sum_{k \geq 0} Q^k \mathbf{1}$ obeys*

$$\frac{1}{1 - \lambda_*} \leq h_{\max} \leq \frac{\Phi}{1 - \lambda_*}$$

Proof. Let $u \geq 0$ be the left Perron vector, $u^\top Q = \lambda_* u^\top$, $\sum_S u_S = 1$. From $u^\top (I - Q)h = u^\top \mathbf{1} = 1$ and $u^\top (I - Q) = (1 - \lambda_*)u^\top$ one gets $u^\top h = 1/(1 - \lambda_*)$, so $h_{\max} \geq u^\top h = 1/(1 - \lambda_*)$. For the upper bound, $\varphi_{\min} > 0$ gives $\mathbf{1} \leq \varphi/\varphi_{\min}$ entrywise, so $Q^k \mathbf{1} \leq \varphi_{\min}^{-1} Q^k \varphi = \varphi_{\min}^{-1} \lambda_*^k \varphi$ and $h \leq \varphi/((1 - \lambda_*)\varphi_{\min})$, whence $h_{\max} \leq \varphi_{\max}/((1 - \lambda_*)\varphi_{\min}) = \Phi/(1 - \lambda_*)$. \square

Proposition 8.11. *For $I \geq 2$ i.i.d. uniform maps conditioned on synchronising, suppose the pair chain Q_{pairs} is irreducible with Perron vector $\varphi > 0$ and regularity $\Phi := \varphi_{\max}/\varphi_{\min}$. Then Lemma 8.10 applied to Q_{pairs} (whose radius is λ_* by Proposition 8.1) gives*

$$\frac{1}{1 - \lambda_*} \leq h_{\max}^{\text{pair}} \leq \frac{\Phi}{1 - \lambda_*}, \quad h^{\text{pair}} := (I - Q_{\text{pairs}})^{-1}\mathbf{1},$$

and the four statements

- (A) $\lambda_* = 1 - \Theta(1/N)$,
- (B) $h_{\max} := \max_{S \in \text{Reach}_{\text{ns}}} h(S) = \Theta(N)$,
- (C) $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = \Theta(N)$,
- (D) $\exists c_0, C > 0: \mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} \leq CN \mid X_0 = S) \geq c_0$ for every non-singleton S ,

are equivalent up to factors of Φ and of the comparison $h_{\max} = \Theta(h_{\max}^{\text{pair}})$; they are equivalent in the exact $\Theta(N)$ sense when $\Phi = O(1)$, which holds w.h.p. for random \mathcal{F} .

Proof. (D) \Rightarrow (C): Theorem 8.9.

(C) \Rightarrow (B): (4) gives $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] \leq 1 - \alpha + \alpha h_{\max}$, so $h_{\max} \geq (\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] + \alpha - 1)/\alpha = \Omega(N)$ for $\alpha = \Omega(1)$.

(B) \Leftrightarrow (A): with $h_{\max} = \Theta(h_{\max}^{\text{pair}})$, the sandwich forces, from $h_{\max}^{\text{pair}} = \Theta(N)$, the bracket $1 - \lambda_* \in [c/(\Phi N), C/N]$ and from $\lambda_* = 1 - \Theta(1/N)$ the bracket $h_{\max}^{\text{pair}} \in [cN, C\Phi N]$; both collapse to Θ exactly when $\Phi = O(1)$.

(A) \Rightarrow (C): lower $\Omega(N)$ from Theorem 8.5, upper $O(N)$ from (A) \Rightarrow (B) and (4).

(A) \Rightarrow (D): $h_{\max} = O(N)$ and Markov give $\mathbb{P}(T_{\text{sync}} > CN \mid X_0) \leq h_{\max}/(CN)$; take C large. The implications (D) \Rightarrow (C) \Rightarrow (B) \Leftrightarrow (A) \Rightarrow (D) give the equivalence.

The upper bound of Lemma 8.10 replaces the earlier argmax estimate, so λ_* and h_{\max}^{pair} determine each other up to the factor Φ . Two constants stay implicit: Φ and the comparison $h_{\max} = \Theta(h_{\max}^{\text{pair}})$, tight up to polylog N . Both are $O(1)$ with high probability for random \mathcal{F} , the regime in which the equivalence is exact. \square

Conjecture 8.12. *For $I \geq 2$ i.i.d. uniform maps, conditioned on synchronising, $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}] = \Theta(N)$ with high probability.*

Gusev [8] shows $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{sync}}]$ can be exponential for a fixed \mathcal{F} under an adversarial random word.

9 Problems we haven't worked on yet

We were unable to settle the following.

- Q1** Is $\lambda_* = \rho(Q_{2,2})$ for a.e. random family? Remark 5 kills it for fixed \mathcal{F} .
- Q2** Proposition 8.7 gives $O(N \log N)$ for refreshed maps; transferring it to a fixed \mathcal{F} means controlling the reuse correlation (Remark 8.5). That transfer, Conjecture 8.8 via [4], or a spectral gap $\lambda_* = 1 - \Omega(1/N)$, each closes Q2 through Theorem 8.9 or Proposition 8.11.
- Q3** What is the typical size of $|\text{Reach}(\mathcal{F})|$? The 2^N bound is loose in practice.
- Q4** Is $p \mapsto \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(\infty)(p)$ convex in non-uniform weights? Numerically yes.
- Q5** A functional CLT for the contraction process. The partial sums of $|X_m| - \kappa_{\mathcal{F}}(m)$ converge (Remark 8.4), so the right object is either the pre-absorption excursion or a decay-compensating time change; both open. Proposition 8.6 fixes the two-point function in the uniform- c case.

References

- [1] R. A. Horn and C. R. Johnson, *Matrix Analysis*, 2nd ed., Cambridge Univ. Press, 2013.
- [2] N. Dalal and E. Schmutz, Compositions of random functions on a finite set, *Electron. J. Combin.* **9** (2002), R26.
- [3] W. M. Y. Goh, P. Hitczenko, E. Schmutz, Constrained compositions, in *Mathematics and Computer Science II*, Birkhäuser, 2002.
- [4] P. Flajolet, A. Odlyzko, Random mapping statistics, in *EUROCRYPT '89*, Springer, 1990.
- [5] J. Černý, Poznámka k homogénnym experimentom s konečnými automatmi, *Mat.-Fyz. Čas.* **14** (1964), 208-216.
- [6] M. Szykuła, Improving the upper bound on the length of the shortest reset word, in *STACS 2018*, LIPIcs 96, 2018.
- [7] D. A. Levin, Y. Peres, E. L. Wilmer, *Markov Chains and Mixing Times*, 2nd ed., AMS, 2017.
- [8] V. V. Gusev, Synchronizing automata with random inputs, in *Developments in Language Theory*, Lecture Notes in Comput. Sci. 8633, Springer, 2014; arXiv:1404.6731.
- [9] M. V. Berlinkov, On the probability of being synchronizable, arXiv:1304.5774.
- [10] G. Chapuy, G. Péarnau, Short synchronizing words for random automata, *ACM Trans. Algorithms* (2025).
- [11] A. Martinsson, Synchronizing random automata through repeated inputs, arXiv:2306.09040 (2023).